

Open Book Futures:

A Study of the digital preservation of e-Theses within UK universities

Authors: See list inside

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Document overview

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Acronyms

Acronyms are written out in full in the first instance, followed by their acronym in parentheses, and from there on in referred to by their acronym.

COPIM	Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
e-Thesis/Theses	Digital version of a graduate student's research project
OA	Open Access
OBF	Open Book Futures
OER	Open Educational Resources

1. Background and Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this report is to describe a series of research studies considering the complexities of the digital preservation of e-Theses as a specific genre of academic writing. The research being reported here has been conducted as part of the Open Book Futures Project, work package 7 *Digital Archiving & Preservation*. It is a phase of the work package concerned with identifying the main issues and challenges associated with archiving and preserving PhD Theses from the perspective of some specific stakeholders. The research was carried out as a collaboration between academics at Loughborough University and practitioners from the Digital Preservation Coalition. The findings of the scoping research have informed the development of Open Education Resources led by the Digital Preservation Coalition.

A PhD thesis is a singular genre of academic writing performing the dual purpose of a piece of scholarly writing but also fulfilling an institution's requirements for the conferring of a degree award upon the author. An e-Thesis is a digital version of a graduate student's research project. Unlike their printed counterparts, e-Theses are stored and shared electronically, offering enhanced accessibility, multimedia integration, and easy searchability. Due to various reasons (perhaps the most important being that, during the COVID-19 pandemic many universities were forced into a rapid decision to require digital only submission of theses) there has been a recent increase in the proliferation of e-Theses. The focus on e-Theses in this report is centred around the important intellectual heritage to be found in these documents and the opportunities for cultural change offered by doctoral students as first-time authors of theses.

As has been noted by Jan & Musadir (2020), doctoral research theses and dissertations are a major source of information, representing key emerging ideas and information and therefore of great value to researchers. Unfortunately, the very nature of such theses and dissertations means that there is a danger that these valued resources can be difficult to locate, being housed in university libraries and archives. The advent of electronic theses and dissertations, however, has provided additional opportunities to increase their visibility and accessibility; notably this will depend on how effectively they are made openly available to others and via which means. As a result, the emergence of open access e-Thesis repositories may prove to be a great advantage for scholarly communication (Jan & Musadir, 2020).

The electronic component of an e-Thesis means that these documents are becoming increasingly complex, with the potential to include a wide variety of digital scholarly content, such as animated data visualisations, interactive stories, and 360-degree VR videos. As a result, there is much debate about what constitutes the main work of a doctoral thesis and that which is supplementary (Shirazi and Zweibel, 2020). For the digital preservation of non-traditional or practice-based e-Theses the challenges and inconsistencies are necessarily

magnified. For example, there is discussion as to whether multimedia files should be considered part of a main thesis work and should, therefore, be ingested and archived alongside the main written component. Alternatively, such files could be considered as ‘supplementary material’ and, therefore, the links to the files would be presented in some way, rather than the files themselves. There is also discussion as to whether multimedia files should be submitted as artefacts (e.g. in their native presentation, such as an interactive story) or pared back to their source files (e.g. software code, audio files, video files). Currently, there is no recourse to universal good practice guidance regarding the archiving and preservation of e-Theses, with guidance varying across institutions.

The capacity within e-Theses for the inclusion of wide variety of digital content would suggest that they could be described as an emerging format, defined by Smith and Cooke (2017) as being complex by nature, and often consisting of more than one media type, such as a combination of film, audio, and text. As noted above, a key challenge in digitally preserving emerging formats can be found in ensuring access to such documents (Rossi et al., 2024).

A key reason for placing a focus on e-Theses is that they have been declared ‘vulnerable’ in the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC)’s ‘Bit List’ of digitally endangered species. This category describes digital materials for which the technical challenges to preservation are modest but responsibility for care is poorly understood, or where the responsible agencies are not meeting preservation need. (2025 DPC BitList). It is believed that research related to the preservation of e-Theses can contribute towards providing the required attention.

As defined by the DPC, “Digital Preservation refers to the series of managed activities necessary to ensure continued access to digital materials for as long as necessary ... (digital preservation) refers to all of the actions required to maintain access to digital materials beyond the limits of media failure or technological and organisational change”. Digital preservation is important because, without frequent attention, digital content is subject to a variety of risks, such as rapid technological change leaving content unusable or unintelligible as the software that interprets it becomes obsolete; a lack of committed resources rendering impossible the storage and management of digital content; and organizational change leaving digital content without a committed custodian. Digital preservation requires a series of actions over time to ensure digital content remains alive, discoverable, accessible and usable (DPC, 2026).

The importance of digital preservation of in the context of e-Theses has been shown by Mirza et al. (2024). This study considers the significance of digitally preserving indigenous scholarly outputs, noting that academic libraries worldwide are becoming more actively involved this activity, mainly through the establishment of Institutional Repositories. This research concentrates on activity within Pakistan, specifically the establishment of an Institutional Repository and the inclusion within it of e-Theses. This is offered as an example for wider uptake.

The specific issues associated with digital preservation mean that it is advisable to consider it in advance of the creation process; this is particularly the case with emerging formats. A framework for support with this concept can be found in the Findable, Impactful, Citable, Usable, Sustainable (FICUS) framework which is arguably an important element of making digital scholarship sustainable (Agate et. al 2021). For sustainable practices in digital preservation of e-Theses it is also important that institutions consider the digital formats that make digital scholarship usable and the descriptive means that make it findable. These factors are also considered by Schöpfel et al. (2025) whose four main tasks in the shift towards e-Theses also include adopting new digital formats and implementing updated bibliographic standards (such as metadata and identifiers). These tasks are particularly relevant when it comes to the increasing use and creation of emerging formats in PhD projects and dissertations.

Based on a limited number of case studies of Nigerian universities Akinola et al. (2024) identified a poor infrastructure for the digital preservation of e-Theses and a reliance on web archiving for the purpose of digital preservation. Similar issues were identified in Mirza et al. (2024), the implication being that valuable scholarly knowledge could be lost. Yet, when it comes to open research narratives the need for digital preservation is often underrepresented and the resources required underplayed.

It is also important to consider the unusual nature of e-Theses in terms of academic writing by noting that e-Theses serve multiple functions (unlike other genres of such writing). Primarily, e-Theses function as the key mechanism for assessment for the award of Doctor of Philosophy; additionally, some thesis material may already have been published in different genres prior to submission. It is also likely that aspects of the submitted thesis will be reworked for different genres after graduation, and some theses may be published in their entirety as monographs. Furthermore, anecdotal evidence suggests that doctoral researchers may not conceive of their thesis as having much purpose beyond the examination viva whilst recognising that the scholarly content holds valuable currency for future publications and later careers. However, as discussed above, there is a school of thought which recognises the important intellectual heritage and knowledge to be found in a PhD thesis.

Where doctoral researchers believe that their thesis is merely a mechanism for assessment, digital preservation might be an afterthought, considered only as part of the final submission. The tension that exists between submission for examination purposes, on the one hand, and dissemination/long-term preservation purposes on the other, means engagement and buy-in across the relevant stakeholders is essential for the meaningful digital preservation of e-Theses. Our argument is that from the outset of their degree programme doctoral researchers need to be made aware of the Open Access agreement under which their work will be shared and the role of discoverability and accessibility in disseminating their thesis as an artefact or scholarly output. This is because the open access deposit and long-term preservation of an e-Thesis

raises fundamental considerations related to capturing important scholarly knowledge. These considerations need to be designed into a thesis from its inception, rather than being subject to post-hoc pre-submission decision making.

This study investigates how, in the view of university library repository staff, doctoral college staff and registry staff, some of the above issues are addressed in current policy and procedures. A secondary question relates to when and how doctoral researchers receive information and guidance about these issues and considerations and their understanding and views on the importance and relevance of digital preservation in relation to their thesis. The aims of the study were therefore as follows:

- To investigate e-Theses preservation practices across universities in the UK
- To explore the extent and existence of relevant preservation policies
- To examine the provision of relevant support and training for doctoral researchers
- To find out how digital materials associated with an E-Thesis are managed for long-term access
- To investigate potential requirements for the education and training resources that would be a direct product of the project

2. Research Design and Methods

2.1 Ethics approach

All the methods in this research involved human participants and were therefore subject to ethical approval. Since Lancaster University is the lead institution for the wider project, clearance was gained via the ethics procedures there. Detail was required on the personal information to be collected, why it was collected, and how it would be stored and protected; this was provided, and ethical approval was granted. Only personal information that was of direct relevance to the research was collected. Prior to data collection, participants were provided with a participant information sheet and explicit consent form. These clearly explained the procedure and process for data collection and storage to the participant and were approved by the Ethics Sub-Committee. Participants signed to confirm that they understood these processes and consented to take part.

2.2 Scoping conversations

The research design was informed by initial conversations with relevant library staff from five UK Higher Education institutions between November 2024 and February 2025. These conversations acted as a preliminary investigation into the existing key procedures and issues in relation to PhD thesis submission and preservation workflows.

Some initial reflections and further details of these conversations can be found in Barnes (2025). Included here is an introduction to the conversations and a further discussion of e-Thesis submission processes and policies, submission practices, practice-based theses, file formats, rights, copyright and licencing, embargoes and longevity, preservation and future access.

The conversations were intended to highlight the issues requiring further investigation and these included the fact that during the pandemic, many universities made a rapid decision to require digital only submission of theses; such an imperative was usually undertaken without necessarily having all the relevant practice, policy and infrastructure in place. In addition, some organisations were not making back-up copies of their digital theses because they were counting on the British Library's EThOS service as a main long-term access and preservation system to ensure that material would be available for the long term. Up until October 2023 EThOS (E-Thesis online Service) formed part of the UK's network of institutional repositories (Gould, 2016). The increase in the number of electronic submissions of theses and the DDOS carried out on EThOS compounded the risk of loss.

An additional issue was that there was no standardised submission process; this was dependent on the practices of the individual institution and included a variety of forms being completed in advance. The process was also being achieved by a variety of individuals (job roles) within each organisation. Findings from the interviews have also highlighted that there are differences between Doctoral College requirements for institutional repository requirements for archiving and digital preservation purposes. The need to update the workflows between these differing services is one of the four main tasks identified by Schöpfel et al. (2025) in the shift towards electronic theses and dissertations.

2.3 Student Survey

A survey was distributed which focused on the views and opinions of research students about how students are supported through the PhD preparation and submission process and how the digital materials which may be a part of a thesis are currently managed for the long term.

The student survey was distributed online and was open to Doctoral students over 18 years of age and expecting to be completing a PhD thesis. The survey contained 18 questions in total and was divided into five sections: Background Information; Understanding and Attitudes; Current Awareness and Practices; Preferences for Training; and Concerns about Long-Term Access and Reuse. Respondents were provided with the following definitions of two relevant terms:

- “Preservation” refers to the actions, policies, and systems that ensure an electronic thesis—and any associated materials—can be accessed, read, and reused reliably over time, regardless of changes in software, file formats, or technology’
- “Electronic thesis” or “e-thesis” refers to the submitted and final version of the doctoral thesis, which may include text, multimedia content, or supplementary files, but does not include the raw data or materials collected to support it (research data)’

The survey was distributed only to doctoral students at the five universities which participated in the online group interviews carried out in December 2025. This was to ensure consistency with the discussions with university staff. The distribution was managed via student mailing lists, a scholarship hub and a doctoral college bulletin.

2.4 Staff Survey

A questionnaire-based survey was designed and distributed that focused on the views and experience of university library and academic registry staff relating to how students are

supported through the PhD preparation and submission process and how the digital materials which may form a part of a thesis are currently managed vis-a-vis digital preservation. The staff survey was distributed online via the following international mailing lists¹ using non-probability sampling techniques:

- DPC-DISCUSSION@JISCMail.AC.UK (which reaches the ~170 international members of the Digital Preservation Coalition)
- DIGITAL-PRESERVATION@JISCMail.AC.UK (a Jisc mailing list managed by the DPC that has subscribers all over the world)
- RESEARCH-DATAMAN@JISCMail.AC.UK (UK-based Jisc mailing list with international subscribers)
- ndsa-all@lists.clir.org (an initiative of the National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program (NDIIPP) of the Library of Congress with ~278 members internationally)

The survey contained 20 questions, which were organised into six sections:

- Background Information
- Institutional Policies and Practices
- Student Needs and Support
- Copyright
- Rights and Content Challenges
- Common Barriers

Respondents were provided with the same definitions of “preservation” and “electronic thesis” as for the student survey (see section 2.3).

2.5 Online group interviews

In December 2025 a series of additional semi-structured group interviews were conducted with doctoral college and library repository staff across five UK Higher Education institutions; all were research intensive. A total of 13 participants took part in the group interviews. The purpose of the groups was to investigate the ways in which doctoral researchers are supported in relation to the production and submission of their PhD theses for long term access purposes and to explore the extent to which digital materials which may form part of a thesis are digitally preserved. Details of the topics and examples of the questions can be found in Table 1 below.

Topic	Example question
Introduction	What is your current role? What does it entail? What do you expect to receive as part of a PhD thesis?
E-Thesis preservation	Does your institution have a remit to carry out preservation activities on e-theses to ensure they can be accessed in the future? Do you have a written policy on preserving e-theses? At what stage in the workflow do you get involved in the process of preserving e-theses?
Training	Does your institution offer any training for on future proofing/preserving e-theses? Does your institution offer any other forms of advice on this subject?
Barriers and challenges	What are the main barriers/challenges to PhD thesis preservation activities at your institution?

Table 1: Overview of interview topics

An interview guide covering the key questions was produced and used in all group interviews to ensure that each one followed a similar format. The key questions were identified via the established expertise of the researchers and through the preliminary informal conversations that had previously taken place. Suitable participants were identified through having had a previous relationship with the researchers conducting the group interviews. The participants were a selection of Open Access and Research managers and digital preservation specialists generally based within the respective Higher Education institution's Library.

The group interviews lasted 45–60 minutes and were recorded with the permission of the participants; this included a transcript which was subsequently used to analyse the discussion. The interviews were conducted online and by the same three researchers.

3. Results

The following section details the findings of each strand of research undertaken within the scoping study.

3.1 Student survey

A total of 106 responses were received; 18 responses with no questions answered were removed from the analysis as were a further four responses with lower than 50% of questions answered. The total number of usable responses was 84. Full details of the findings of the survey can be found in Appendix A.

Table 2 shows the responses to a question asking participants to provide details of their primary field or discipline. Respondents were able to select all which applied. As can be seen from the Table, the highest proportion of participants were from the Sciences. 'Other' responses were Nursing and Games.

	No	%
Sciences	57	67.9
Humanities	14	16.7
Engineering	13	15.5
Social Sciences	12	14.3
Arts & Design	10	11.9
Computer & Data Sciences	8	9.5
Education & Communication	7	8.3
Mathematics	4	4.8
Business & Management	0	0.0
Law & Policy	0	0.0
Other	3	3.6
Responses	84	

Table 2: What is your primary field or discipline? (Select all that apply)

Table 3 shows that the majority (44.0%) of the respondents were in the data collection, analysis and/or experimentation stage of their doctoral study. With regard to the 'other' category, no additional doctoral stages were noted.

	No	%
Data collection, analysis, and/or experimentation	37	44.0
Writing thesis	27	32.1

Just starting/planning research	25	29.8
Post-submission/defence completed	9	10.7
Near submission	6	7.1
Other	2	2.4
Responses	84	

Table 3: What stage of your doctoral research are you currently in?

It was important to investigate the kinds of theses which were being produced by respondents; Table 4 shows that the majority were planning a traditional text-based thesis (60.7%).

Significantly, around a third of respondents (36.9%) noted that their thesis would be a text-based thesis accompanied by supplementary files. ‘Other’ formats noted were as follows: an App; an exhibition; a PhD with publications; a practice portfolio plus thesis.

	No	%
A traditional text-based thesis (PDF or equivalent)	51	60.7
A text-based thesis accompanied by supplementary files (e.g., datasets, software/code, multimedia)	31	36.9
A text-based thesis with substantial embedded multimedia (e.g., audio, video, images)	23	27.4
A fully multimedia, non-text, or creative work	2	2.4
A website	1	1.2
Not sure	6	7.1
Other	1	1.2
Responses	84	

Table 4: What type of thesis are you producing or planning to produce?

The majority of respondents (97.6%) noted that a text document would be a constituent part of their submitted thesis (not including research data or datasets), and approximately three quarters (72.3%) claimed that images or graphics would also feature (see Table 5). ‘Other’ elements noted were stereoscope(s) and accompanying artefacts; and musical scores, including digital performance materials.

	No	%
Text documents (e.g., Word, PDF)	81	97.6
Images or graphics	60	72.3
Software or code	25	30.1
Spreadsheets (e.g., Excel, CSV) or databases	24	28.9
Audio or video files	9	10.8
Web pages or interactive content	8	9.6
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	4	4.8

Not sure	2	2.4
3D data	1	1.2
Other	5	6.0
Responses	83	

Table 5: What types of files or materials will be included as part of your submitted thesis?

Table 6 shows that the majority of respondents (77.4%) found it to be at least 'very important' that their doctoral thesis can be accessed and reused in the long term by future researchers. A further 16.7% found it 'moderately important'.

	No	%
Extremely important	41	48.8
Very important	24	28.6
Moderately important	14	16.7
Slightly important	3	3.6
Not at all important	2	2.4
Total	84	100

Table 6: How important do you think it is that your doctoral thesis can be accessed and reused in the long term by future researchers?

However, in contrast 65.8% claimed to either 'not very confident' or 'not confident at all' about knowing what steps to take to help ensure their thesis could be preserved, accessed and reused in the long term. In addition, around half of the participants recognised that they might need to take responsibility in this regard – see Table 7.

	No	%
Maybe, I might need to take some steps	31	36.9
Not really, I assume it will be preserved automatically	25	29.8
Yes, this is mainly my responsibility	12	14.3
No, that's entirely my university's responsibility	8	9.5
Not sure	4	4.8
Other	4	4.8
Total	84	100

Table 7: Do you think you need to do anything yourself to make sure your thesis can still be accessed and reused in the future?

The great majority (86.9%) were at least 'somewhat interested' in learning simple steps to be taken to help ensure their thesis could be preserved and accessible in the future.

When considering the steps that had been taken by respondents to help to ensure that their e-Thesis would remain accessible in the future, the picture was varied. Around half had used open or widely supported file formats for text, data or code (52.4%), and a similar number had deposited or were planning to deposit their thesis in an institutional or disciplinary repository (51.2%). Around 40% had created backups in multiple locations (44.0%) and organised and documented their thesis files and research data (39.3%).

When asked whether their university offers any guidance or training on preserving electronic theses for long-term access and reuse, the great majority (70.7%) were 'not sure'. Of the remainder, 19.5% responded 'yes' and 9.8% responded 'no'. Anecdotal evidence suggests that students might be receiving the appropriate training but be unaware that its purpose is related to thesis preservation.

Preferences for training were for 'a written guide or checklist' (44.4%) and 'a short online module (self-paced)' (22.2%). Just 19.8% expressed a wish for 'a live online workshop or webinar' and 11.1% for 'a short video or animation'. One participant suggested combining a module with a guide or checklist. In terms of time spent, the majority preferred 15-30 minutes in duration (39.0%) or 30-60 minutes (35.4%).

When asked about the topics they would find most useful, the responses indicate an interest on the part of the respondents. As noted by one respondent, 'All of the above is important!'. Table 8 shows the variety of responses, with the relatively high proportion selecting 'managing rights, permissions, or copyright' demonstrating an alliance with staff comments in evidence during the group interviews. It is notable that comments were also made during the interviews relating to 'understanding university policies and workflows' (28.0%).

	No	%
Managing rights, permissions, or copyright	49	59.8
Organising and documenting files for future access and reuse	34	41.5
Choosing files formats that are suitable for long-term preservation	33	40.2
Depositing your thesis in institutional or subject repositories	31	37.8
Ensuring that links, online sources, and other external materials that you cite remain accessible over time	28	34.1
Understanding university policies and workflows	23	28.0
Preserving multimedia content (e.g., images, video, audio, code, websites) for future access and reuse	21	25.6
Other	6	7.3
Responses	82	

Table 8: Which of the following topics would you find most useful in training on how to preserve your thesis for long-term access and reuse? (Select up to three)

With regard to concerns about long-term access and reuse, the responses showed that participants had some understanding of the potential problems that might arise. Table 9 shows the responses received, with the highest proportion being concerned that their thesis will not be discoverable or accessible online (66.7%). It is also notable that 47.6% thought that rights or permissions could limit access and 40.5% being aware of the danger of links or other digital components ceasing to be viable.

	No	%
That people won't be able to find or access my thesis online	56	66.7
That rights or permissions (e.g., use of third-party materials) could limit access	40	47.6
That links, media, or other digital components in my thesis might stop working	34	40.5
That the file formats I use might not be readable in the future	31	36.9
That my thesis won't be preserved properly by my university	28	33.3
Other	6	7.1
Responses	84	

Table 9: When you think about the long-term preservation of your thesis, what (if anything) concerns you the most? (Select up to three)

Participants were provided with space to raise any other issues they wished to share about long-term access to and use of their PhD thesis. A key issue related to potential embargoes on access to the thesis, due to supervisors not wishing the research to be available externally. Another had been discouraged from publishing any raw data by their supervisor but was worried that this could undermine the validity of the findings. They were interested in the practices of other doctoral students in this regard and what steps might be taken to avoid plagiarism or intellectual theft.

However, another respondent suggested that it would be interesting to have a clearer default link between a thesis and the publications directly originating from it; they noted that their institution requires all publications to be open access thereby facilitating access generally.

Another respondent noted understanding the fragility of research preservation and a second noted that the physical body of the work is important for the long-term historical record, leading them to hope it can be preserved properly.

Importantly, respondents took the time to note their knowledge relating to the transitory nature of formats and emerging technology. They expressed the wish that the University will take on the responsibility for providing storage and long-term access.

3.2 Staff survey

A total of 136 responses were received; 41 responses with no questions answered were removed from the analysis as were a further six responses with 33% or fewer questions answered and two 'test' responses. As a result, the total number of usable responses was 87.

Full details of the responses to the survey can be found in Appendix B. The number of responses was below the threshold to achieve reliable results from statistical tests such as the Pearson correlation test, so we have reported the actual numbers / percentages only.

3.3 Group interviews

Given that an in-depth investigation of the digital preservation of PhD e-Theses was required, a thematic (bottom up) approach was employed for data analysis (Braun & Clarke 2006). This allowed themes to develop both from the research questions and the narratives of research participants.

Transcripts were derived from the group interview recordings which comprised of 264 minutes in total and were anonymised/de-identified and then analysed by a team of two researchers using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke 2006), one of the most widely used methods for analysing qualitative data, offering a structured yet flexible approach to identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns or themes within a dataset (Ahmed et al., 2025). Specifically, Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis framework was employed. One of the researchers analysing the data was present at all five group interviews, the other was a member of the project team and had expertise in the subject.

The first phase (familiarisation with data) involved the two researchers immersing themselves in the transcripts (the raw data) by reading and re-reading, actively engaging with the material and noting initial ideas and potential patterns or links. As a result of the familiarisation the researchers moved to the second phase and generated some initial codes and then to the third phase involving searching for themes. The fourth phase involved the two researchers meeting to discuss and review the themes which they had decided on independently, leading to the defining and agreeing of the final themes. The sixth and final phase involves reporting the analysis: four main themes were identified as follows:

- Perceptions: of repository/library staff, students and academic staff
- Policies and priorities: of the institutions
- Systems: includes repository systems, file formats and access and so on
- Skills and training: of repository/library staff, students and academic staff

3.3.1 Perceptions

The theme of perceptions relates to the perceptions of both repository staff and library staff, and to doctoral students and academic staff who act as their supervisors.

There were inconsistencies in the level of digital preservation knowledge across those interviewed. They were not quite sure whether this referred to adding material to the repository and had not always considered the specific requirements of digital preservation. Organisational policies relating to digital preservation were in existence, but they did not always encompass e-Theses specifically. In addition, perceptions of what makes a 'good' repository varied across the institutions, with some being unsure about the material they should be acquiring or not taking into consideration future proofing of their repository. It was also notable that the institutional policy did not always line up with the repository policy.

Perceptions related to the definition of a thesis can be seen in the responses to a direct question asking interviewees how they would define a thesis. The interviewees clearly understood the intellectual component, that is, the mental or cognitive aspect of the thesis. However, when discussing the status of a thesis as a research object or a publication, interviewees suggested that student perceptions were that the thesis is essentially a requirement for gaining a research degree rather than a publication in its own right. The focus was generally on publishing the thesis as a monograph or one or more journal articles and the potential for a thesis to act as an independent publication was somewhat disregarded. In addition, there was much uncertainty around the consequences on preservation of more practice-based theses which might include materials which are not text-based, for example, audio or visual files.

It is significant that the security risks of relying on the e-Thesis was also cited with the EThOS hacking incident remaining uppermost in some interviewees' minds. This aligns with the findings of the scoping conversations discussed above.

3.3.2 Policies and priorities

When considering the policies and priorities it was found that institutional priorities were not particularly clear to the interviewees and there was a lack of written policies within their organisation to help them to understand the key concerns relating to digital preservation of e-Theses within their own organisation. In addition, there was sometimes a disconnect between preservation activities and the e-Thesis workflow; furthermore, staff involved in the e-Thesis submission workflow were not necessarily fully aware of the true meaning of digital preservation or how it relates to their own work.

The emphasis was more on short-term access than on long-term preservation. This was influenced by the idea of the e-Thesis as a back-up to the hard copy (in cases where a hard copy was required); it is potentially a less complicated endeavour to preserve a printed copy of a thesis. However, one interviewee did comment, 'you can't have access long-term without preservation'.

The group interviews showed that digital submission was mostly reactive rather than proactive. The move to digital was in part a response to the restrictions which resulted from the lockdown associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. Once institutions had introduced digital submission, they had not rescinded it, although some participants noted that hard copies were still required.

It was notable that e-Thesis submission requirements were often part of an administrative process, with the completion of a range of online and printed forms being necessary. The forms were also often connected to the proposed access level of the e-Thesis.

Taking into account the idea that a repository that provides current management of and access to digital content is not always the same as a repository that carries out full digital preservation (as defined on page 3), it was not clear whether all participants fully understood the difference. In addition, the participants were generally not aware of how to preserve material and there was some debate over whether it was their responsibility, or that of other individuals within the organisation.

There was much discussion related to thesis access and embargoes; this tended to centre around open access or restricted access or a compromise somewhere between the two extremes. It was an issue on which the participants stated needing guidance. Often the embargoes on e-Thesis access were due to sponsor requests or sensitive material that was contained within the thesis and were for a specific period of time (usually 12 months) which is extendable on request. It also emerged that there exist students who are under the misapprehension that they will be unable to publish material from their thesis in external sources if their thesis is openly available in the University repository. The participants stressed that this misunderstanding relating to open access and publication was also held by supervisors and could often be erroneously passed on to their students.

3.3.3 Technical practices

The theme of technical practices included repository systems, file formats and short-term versus long-term access. The group interviews found that the repository systems software being employed was variable across institutions. This means that there was a lack of standardisation in aspects such as access, and in the processes for thesis submission (online and physical) and deposit.

File formats required for submission were similarly variable, although there was a predominance of expectation for PDF files. Where a thesis would include files other than text-based files there was some evidence of a lack of guidance or policy on which other file formats were suitable for deposit alongside the PDF text. It is notable that all interviewees claimed there was no reason for which they would refuse to accept a thesis and were proactive in ensuring all e-Theses could be admitted, albeit that they might need to request an alternative version in a different file format or additional paperwork if it was missing.

The group interviews uncovered an emphasis on access systems with participants concentrating on levels of access of thesis materials rather than on their digital preservation. Security risks were also relevant to systems, it being necessary to ensure that security is embedded appropriately in the physical and administrative systems. This theme was also considered in the analysis of perceptions.

Concerns around rights clearance were also discussed, with a focus on this issue being uppermost in some institutions. In certain cases, the participants noted being required to investigate rights and copyright clearance and any licences which had been acquired to reproduce figures or images; they would usually pass the responsibility back to the students concerned. Unsurprisingly, as a result, it was clearly often a concern for students.

Discussions around preservation scalability demonstrated that the participants were wary and therefore keen to begin on a limited basis in order to subsequently scale up.

Some interviewees noted their practice of storing any additional or associated files with the textual thesis; this included data files.

3.3.4 Skills and training

There was a variety of skills and training issues which were included in this theme. These related to repository and library staff as well as the doctoral students themselves and their supervisors (academic staff). It is notable firstly that there was a general skills gap regarding digital preservation of e-Theses; this related to the group interview participants (repository and library staff) but also the students and their supervisors. This could often lead to misapprehensions on the part of the supervisor, with the consequence that they could be passing on misinformation to their students. This has already been discussed above in the consideration of the use of embargoes on e-Theses.

Pre-preservation training activities were varied, sometimes being carried out by the participants themselves but also by other staff such as those in the organisation's Doctoral College or equivalent. Notably more than one of the group interviews included a mention of Lib Guides, a key way in which library staff pass on information to their users.

For some institutions the reactive nature of requiring electronic submission meant that there had been little consideration of e-Thesis preservation. In other organisations where preservation had been considered, light touch treatment (rather than rigorous preservation) was thought to be sufficient.

It was notable that in general the involvement of the library and/or repository staff was likely to occur at the end of the study period (close to the student's submission) when it was perhaps too late to think about how the thesis would best be preserved for long term access. That is to say, the majority of decisions relevant for digital preservation are likely to have already been made at an earlier stage in the development of the PhD thesis. This finding endorses the debate over where the responsibility lies for digital preservation; whether this should belong to the institution, the student, the supervisor, or to a combination of all three stakeholders.

4. Discussion

4.1 Perceptions

The study has shown that for the majority of research participants there is a limited understanding of what digital preservation entails. There were some notable exceptions to this where participating universities have clear priorities and policies vis-a-digital preservation of e-Theses, but in general terms, this limited understanding is evident in both the student and staff survey and the group interview data. Where university libraries have digital preservation specialists in-situ, they are providing valuable expertise and advocacy, but they reported the necessity to educate and influence institutional policy makers as being a complex challenge.

Although digital preservation policies exist within universities, oftentimes they do not explicitly include PhD theses within their remit, focusing instead on other types of scholarly outputs. An explanation for this could be a failure to recognise the unique nature and characteristics of e-Theses and their vulnerability regarding digital preservation for long-term access. There is often uncertainty regarding what constitutes a thesis or open access book, especially in relation to datasets, multimedia and software components, leading to e-Theses (together with open monographs) being often perceived as static, single-file outputs rather than evolving digital objects requiring continuing attention. This means that digital preservation of such digital objects can be misunderstood or neglected; it is notable that, since most e-Theses are theoretically open access this shows additional limited understanding of preservation requirements for other open access works. In the context of a project like Open Book Futures, it could be argued that this implies that there is a general limited understanding of preservation requirements and lack of knowledge related to best practice for open access works.

Perceptions related to the definition of a thesis are clear in their relation to the intellectual component, although the finding that students view it primarily as a requirement for gaining their degree potentially impacts whether they conceive of it as a publication and a contribution to research in its own right. This in turn can affect understanding of digital preservation requirements.

Perceptions around repository practices are varied both in terms of the material which is being acquired and the ways in which future proofing is ensured. The differences between institutional policy and repository policy are likely to be a key factor in shaping perceptions.

4.2 Policies and Responsibilities

When considering policies and priorities related to the digital preservation of e-Theses, it was found that institutional priorities were not particularly clear to the interviewees and that the emphasis within such policies was more on short-term access than on long-term access via digital preservation. With regard to e-Theses in particular, there was a lack of written policies within organisations to help staff understand the key concerns relating to digital preservation. In addition, there were administrative processes which were specific to e-Thesis submission, that differed to more general repository acquisition, which students and supervisors often found difficult to navigate.

Across the participants in the staff survey and group interviews there was a lack of consensus as to where primary responsibility sits within university structures for ensuring that e-Theses are created using appropriate formats for long-term digital preservation. For example, whether it should be students, supervisors, repository staff or other individuals within the organization. Similarly, it is not clear who bears the responsibility for digital preservation training and upskilling and for the long-term stewardship of e-Theses to ensure their continuing access and use.

The specific characteristics of e-Theses mean that they tend to be affected by embargoes, with permitted access to e-Theses ranging from immediate open access to restricted access; often a compromise between the two is established. The handling of embargoes is inconsistent across institutions, not least because of students' and supervisors' lack of understanding of the copyright and open access landscape. For example, students expressed concern that they would be unable to publish material from their thesis if it is made openly available in their institution's repository. Similarly, there are inconsistent practices regarding copyright clearance within both the main body of an e-Theses and any associated material. Thus, the situation regarding onward publication is often misunderstood by both students and supervisors and is an area where openly available online training resources and guidance would be of benefit.

4.3 Technical practices

Technical practices are dependent on the specific repository system that libraries subscribe to. Given that there are several different repository systems in use it is unsurprising that technical practices varied across university libraries since different systems support different functions. Consequently, variability of repository systems has led to a lack of standardisation of practices. It is relevant to note here that whilst some repository systems offer basic Bit preservation functions those UK universities that do have active digital preservation policies invest in an additional preservation system.

University and repository-level policies also influence technical practices and oftentimes these practices are agnostic of any specific repository system. For example, the requirement by some university libraries for e-Theses to be submitted both in the original file format and as a PDF version. This technical practice is driven by a library's digital preservation policy, rather than repository system requirements or constraints.

Whilst the guidance regarding file formats for the deposit of the main body of the e-Thesis was clear, there was little, or unclear, documented guidance regarding file formats for supplementary files. From a digital preservation perspective this is problematic, as Turpin (2025) explains, advance guidance about appropriate file formats for archiving and preservation would have positively influenced choices made earlier in her PhD research regarding the creation and storage of multimedia files.

The bespoke nature of e-Theses presents challenges for the scalability of digital preservation practices within university libraries. The findings show that establishing the preservation needs of theses that are not traditional, predominantly, text-based theses necessitate detailed engagement with the content of those theses and mediation across different understandings and skill levels. Given that the results of the student survey show that 37% of respondents reported that they were producing a text-based thesis accompanied by supplementary files (e.g., datasets, software/code, multimedia) and 27% A text-based thesis with substantial embedded multimedia (e.g., audio, video, images), scalability is an element that needs addressing across the sector.

4.4 Skills and Training

The research uncovered significant preservation skills gaps among academic supervisors, students and administrative staff; this was evident from responses made to the student survey and during both the scoping conversations and the online group interviews. This generally related to the digital preservation of e-Theses, particularly where other digital preservation expertise was more widespread. The skills gaps have led to an important aspect of the project involved the production of some relevant Open Educational Resources (OER).

It was also found that training is often generic, optional or delivered at the end of the doctoral process. There were examples of training being offered which participants did not recognise as being related to digital preservation. There were some good examples of attempts being made to offer relevant training which was optional and therefore not widely attended; this suggests that students and supervisors are not sufficiently aware of the nature and importance of the training. Mandatory training could mitigate some of these issues and might avoid the misapprehensions of supervisors relating to publication potential of PhD theses.

The concerns raised relating to skills and training suggest that opportunities exist for early interventions which could be more specifically targeted. This might, in turn, feed into the debate over where the responsibility lies for e-Thesis preservation – whether this lies with the institution, the student, the supervisor, or with a combination of all three stakeholders.

5. Policy Recommendations

This section is taken from the Work Package 7 Archiving and Digital Preservation: Policy Recommendations for National and International Policy Makers report (DOI ...).

1. Where e-Theses are university mandated and where possible - excluding those that have been embargoed, have copyright considerations or similar - e-Theses should be open access and openly available and digitally preserved

For e-Theses to be open access they should be openly available with all the associated files being freely available to view and download by any reader with access to the internet through a university repository or other relevant repository (e.g. through the British Library's EthOS platform). This recommendation is intended for university policy makers and university repositories.

2. There should be UK wide consistency and an agreement on the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses and their associated digital materials, and the approach for archiving and preserving digital materials and creative outputs that form the main body of the doctoral submission

This recommendation relates to findings in the research that there is currently no recourse to universal good practice guidance regarding the archiving and preservation of e-Theses, with guidance varying across institutions. It also relates to the findings around lack of awareness and knowledge in university staff and students around digitally complex PhD outputs and non-traditional Theses. This recommendation is intended for policymakers operating policy for UK universities, as well as national organisations in a position to agree best practice in these areas.

3. Responsibilities should be clarified across the different aspects of the approach for archiving and preserving e-Theses within and across universities, including for staff and student training and ownership over the associated systems

This recommendation relates to findings in the research about disagreement and confusion around the responsibility for initially ensuring e-Theses are created in the correct format to be preserved in the long-term and whether this responsibility lies with students, supervisors, repository staff or other individuals within the organization. Furthermore, it was found that it is not clear who bears the responsibility for training and learning around digital preservation and for the long-term stewardship of e-Theses to ensure their continuing access and use. This recommendation is intended mostly for policy makers in universities; however it does also relate

to the previous recommendation in that these responsibilities should form part of a UK-wide agreement on the approach for archiving and digitally preserving PhD Theses.

4. Doctoral training regarding data management and digitally preserving e-Theses should be mandated to be made available to both doctoral researchers and PhD supervisors from the point at which it is needed; and universities should utilise openly shared training materials, as well as making their own openly available

This recommendation relates to the findings around challenges faced in skills and training relating to digital preservation in universities, and to the conclusion that training is needed much earlier in the PhD process, as opposed to information being focussed solely around PhD submission. It also relates to the Digital Preservation Coalition open educational resources created as part of Open Book Futures, and in recognition of the importance of sharing practice across institutions. This recommendation is intended for university policy makers as well as for individuals and teams within universities responsible for providing information about and access to training.

5. As part of university training around scholarly communication and publishing, cognate to digital preservation, students and staff should be made aware of the need for long-term access and how this relates to issues such as embargoes, copyright and so on

This recommendation relates to findings emanating from the research around the perception and awareness of open access publications and digital preservation, and how the perceptions of staff such as PhD supervisors have an impact on the perception of students and therefore the actions they take or do not take in digitally preserving their PhD Thesis. It also relates to findings around misunderstanding specifically on issues such as embargoes and copyright leading to PhD Theses in some cases being unnecessarily closed access. This recommendation is intended for university policy makers, particularly those involved in university training, not just for PhD students and doctoral researchers, but also for academic training more generally.

6. References

- Agate, N., Ball, C., Belan, A., McCormick, M., and Neds-Fox, J. (2021). Findable, Impactful, Citable, Usable, Sustainable (FICUS): A Heuristic for Digital Publishing. *In: [Shaping the Digital Dissertation: Knowledge Production in the Arts and Humanities](#)* (pp. 83–104). DOI: [10.11647/OBP.0239.06](https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0239.06)
- Ahmed, S.K., Mohammed, R.A., Nashwan, A.J., Ibrahim, R.H., Abdalla, A.Q., Ameen, B.M.M. & Khahir, R.M. (2025) Using thematic analysis in qualitative research. *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health*, 6, August 2025, 100198.
DOI: [10.1016/j.glmedi.2025.100198](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2025.100198)
- Akinola, A., Oso, O.O., Shorunke, O.A., and Oyadele, O.G. (2024) Preservation of theses and dissertations in the era of digitization: a case study of selected universities in Oyo state, Nigeria. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 40 (4), pp. 631–648. DOI: [10.1108/DLP-03-2024-0053](https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-03-2024-0053)
- Barnes, M. (2025). Scoping PhD Theses: Some initial reflections. *Copim*. DOI: [10.21428/785a6451.d98f9a16](https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.d98f9a16)
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3(2), 77-101.
- DPC Bit List (2025) The Global List of Endangered Materials. Available from <http://doi.org/10.7207/dpcbitlist-25>
- DPC (2026) What is Digital Preservation? [What is digital preservation? - Digital Preservation Coalition](#)
- Gould, S. (2016) UK theses and the British Library EThOS service: from supply on demand to repository linking. *Interlending & Document Supply*, 44(1): 7–13. DOI: [10.1108/ILDS-10-2015-0033](https://doi.org/10.1108/ILDS-10-2015-0033)
- Jan, S. & Mudasir, K. (2020) The Global Contribution of E-Theses and Dissertations (ETD): Growth and Development in the Digital Era. *International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries*, 5(1), 1-8.
- Mirza, K. B., Arif, M., Ullah, M., & Hamid, M. (2024). Unlocking Scholarly Access Beyond Boundaries: Strategies, Lessons, and Challenges in Implementing an Institutional Repository at Quaid I Azam University Library, Pakistan. *The International Information & Library Review*, 56(4), 335–351. DOI: [10.1080/10572317.2024.2402674](https://doi.org/10.1080/10572317.2024.2402674)

Rossi, G. C., Cooke, I., Clark, L., Pyke, T., & Smith Nicholls, F. (2024). User-centred collecting for emerging formats. *New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia*, 30(1–2), pp. 114–128. DOI: [10.1080/13614568.2024.2389101](https://doi.org/10.1080/13614568.2024.2389101)

Schöpfel, J., Boock, M., Rasuli, B., & van Wyk, B. (2025). New Frontiers of Electronic Theses and Dissertations. *Encyclopedia*, 5(1), 6. DOI: [10.3390/encyclopedia5010006](https://doi.org/10.3390/encyclopedia5010006)

Shirazi, R., and Zweibel, S. (2020). Documenting Digital Projects: Instituting Guidelines for Digital Dissertations and Theses in the Humanities. *College & Research Libraries*, 81(7), p. 1123. DOI: [10.5860/crl.81.7.1123](https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.7.1123)

Smith, C., & Cooke, I. (2017). Emerging formats: Complex digital media and its impact on the UK legal deposit libraries. *Alexandria: The Journal of National and International Library and Information Issues*, 27(3), 175–187. DOI: [10.1177/0955749018775878](https://doi.org/10.1177/0955749018775878)

Appendices

Appendix A: Student survey results

What is your primary field or discipline? (Select all that apply)

	No	%
Sciences	57	67.9
Humanities	14	16.7
Engineering	13	15.5
Social Sciences	12	14.3
Arts & Design	10	11.9
Computer & Data Sciences	8	9.5
Education & Communication	7	8.3
Mathematics	4	4.8
Business & Management	0	0.0
Law & Policy	0	0.0
Other	3	3.6
Responses	84	

Other:

- Nursing
- Games

What stage of your doctoral research are you currently in?

	No	%
Data collection, analysis, and/or experimentation	37	44.0
Writing thesis	27	32.1
Just starting/planning research	25	29.8
Post-submission/defence completed	9	10.7
Near submission	6	7.1
Other	2	2.4
Responses	84	

Other: none specified

What type of thesis are you producing or planning to produce?

	No	%

A traditional text-based thesis (PDF or equivalent)	51	60.7
A text-based thesis accompanied by supplementary files (e.g., datasets, software/code, multimedia)	31	36.9
A text-based thesis with substantial embedded multimedia (e.g., audio, video, images)	23	27.4
A fully multimedia, non-text, or creative work	2	2.4
A website	1	1.2
Not sure	6	7.1
Other	1	1.2
Responses	84	

Other:

- An app
- A text
- An exhibition
- PhD with publications
- Practice portfolio plus thesis

What types of files or materials will be included as part of your submitted thesis? (Please consider only content that will form part of your final thesis, not research data or datasets)

	No	%
Text documents (e.g., Word, PDF)	81	97.6
Images or graphics	60	72.3
Software or code	25	30.1
Spreadsheets (e.g., Excel, CSV) or databases	24	28.9
Audio or video files	9	10.8
Web pages or interactive content	8	9.6
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	4	4.8
Not sure	2	2.4
3D data	1	1.2
Other	5	6.0
Responses	83	

Other:

- Stereoscope(s) and accompanying artefacts
- Musical scores, including digital performance materials

Understanding and Attitudes

How important do you think it is that your doctoral thesis can be accessed and reused in the long term by future researchers?

	No	%
Extremely important	41	48.8
Very important	24	28.6
Moderately important	14	16.7
Slightly important	3	3.6
Not at all important	2	2.4
Total	84	100

Do you think you need to do anything yourself to make sure your thesis can still be accessed and reused in the future?

	No	%
Maybe, I might need to take some steps	31	36.9
Not really, I assume it will be preserved automatically	25	29.8
Yes, this is mainly my responsibility	12	14.3
No, that's entirely my university's responsibility	8	9.5
Not sure	4	4.8
Other	4	4.8
Total	84	100

Other:

- It should be shared by the university and the student, and the national or similar library
- It is my responsibility, but the institutions that I work with provide some dedicated support which I will make use of (CERN)
- I have a traditional thesis and a practice journal detailing my practical investigation and all the finished filmed performances. My problem is how to present my practice journals. I have looked at ISUU and other digital flip book providers. I can get a year free from them but pay yearly thereafter. I want my work accessible but not totally public. Only for those who apply to access the thesis and accompanying
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future

How confident do you feel about knowing what steps to take to help ensure your thesis can be preserved, accessed, and reused in the long term?

	No	%
Not very confident	32	39.0
Not confident at all	22	26.8
Somewhat confident	21	25.6
Very confident	4	4.9
Other	3	3.7
Total	82	100

Other:

- I do not know how to get the University to preserve it, but I know how to get all the files I need to try and preserve it myself
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future
- For documents like text and scores, I feel confident. However, future compatibility of proprietary software is largely out of my hands and beyond my technical expertise

How interested would you be in learning simple steps you can take to help ensure your thesis is preserved and accessible in the future?

	No	%
Very interested	36	42.9
Somewhat interested	37	44.0
Not very interested	6	7.1
Not interested at all	2	2.4
Other	3	3.6
Total	84	100

Other:

- Will only do if it's a requirement from the university. Otherwise all data, codes, pipelines or work have their values: they are more likely to be disseminated through academic publications, open to the world by voluntary preference, commercialised through startups or be kept private to the research lab only
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future

Current Awareness and Practices

Which of the following steps, if any, have you taken to help you ensure that your PhD thesis will remain accessible in the long term?

	No	%
Used open or widely supported file formats for text, data, or code	44	52.4
Deposited or plan to deposit my thesis in an institutional or disciplinary repository	43	51.2
Created backups in multiple locations (e.g., institutional storage, secure cloud, external drives)	37	44.0
Organized and documented my thesis files and research data (e.g., clear folder structure, README files)	33	39.3
I have not taken any steps yet	23	27.4
Followed guidance or requirements from my institution or funder on long-term access	13	15.5
Applied metadata, documentation, or version control to my files	12	14.3

I do not plan to take any steps	1	1.2
Not sure	0	0.0
Other	4	4.8
Responses	84	

Other:

- I have a github where my data and code are (not well) accessible and curated. Some of my thesis is already published as papers where accessibility and data management seems more robust
- I figure the obvious way is to publish your work in other venues - same content as the PhD, but more accessible; github repo?
- I am aware of the need to make backups but I don't know how to do so easily

Does your university offer any guidance or training on preserving electronic theses for long-term access and reuse?

	No	%
Not sure	58	70.7
Yes	16	19.5
No	8	9.8
Total	82	100

Have you participated in any of this training or read any of the guidance?

	No	%
No – other reason	38	50.0
No, I didn't have time	16	21.1
No, I didn't think it was relevant	14	18.4
Yes	12	15.8
Responses	76	

Other reason for the above:

Unaware/unsure if it is offered	18
Not yet/too early	7
Haven't thought about it	1
Just starting the PhD	1
Not the first priority	1
Planning to do so	1
Total	29

How helpful was the training or guidance that you received?

Somewhat helpful	9
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Very helpful	1
Not very helpful	1
Not helpful at all	0
Other	0
Total	11

What was the main reason that you found it helpful or not helpful?

- Provided information and resources I could come back to throughout and closer to periods when I felt I had the time/need to do
- My primary focus is to find a relevant institutional holder
- I mostly knew what to do already
- My thesis can be accessed widely
- PhD students need clear instructions and the majority of the courses, albeit conducted by kind instructors, were more about the social difficulties (ie how to get your thesis done from a mental perspective) as opposed to how to actually structure your thesis in a coherent manner.
- Wasn't sure how to apply it to my own work
- Thinking about data management from start to finish
- Explained creative commons licenses which was helpful and interesting
- Preferences for Training

If you were offered training on how to make your thesis more easily preserved and reusable, what format would you most prefer?

	No	%
A written guide or checklist	36	44.4
A short online module (self-paced)	18	22.2
A live online workshop or webinar	16	19.8
A short video or animation	9	11.1
Other	2	2.5
Total	81	100

Other: Both a training and checklist

How much time in total would you be willing to spend on this kind of training?

	No	%
15-30 minutes	32	39.0
30-60 minutes	29	35.4
More than an hour	10	12.2
Less than 15 minutes	8	9.8
Other	3	3.7

Total	82	100
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Other: Recurring 30-minute classes for each stage (e.g. planning, data collection, writing up)

Which of the following topics would you find most useful in training on how to preserve your thesis for long-term access and reuse? (Select up to three)

	No	%
Managing rights, permissions, or copyright	49	59.8
Organising and documenting files for future access and reuse	34	41.5
Choosing files formats that are suitable for long-term preservation	33	40.2
Depositing your thesis in institutional or subject repositories	31	37.8
Ensuring that links, online sources, and other external materials that you cite remain accessible over time	28	34.1
Understanding university policies and workflows	23	28.0
Preserving multimedia content (e.g., images, video, audio, code, websites) for future access and reuse	21	25.6
Other	6	7.3
Responses	82	

- All of the above is important!
- Some debunking of data preservation main misconceptions
- The submission process should automatically prevent me from submitting something in a form that wouldn't be suitable for long term preservation anyway. The burden for checking this should not be on the student, because then it won't be done
- Version control during writing up
- The licenses of the software packages I used and for each license type, my obligation to reproduce my derivative to the open world. Please that's way more important than open sourcing my thesis!
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future

Concerns About Long-Term Access and Reuse

When you think about the long-term preservation of your thesis, what (if anything) concerns you the most? (Select up to three)

	No	%
That people won't be able to find or access my thesis online	56	66.7
That rights or permissions (e.g., use of third-party materials) could limit access	40	47.6
That links, media, or other digital components in my thesis might stop working	34	40.5
That the file formats I use might not be readable in the future	31	36.9

That my thesis won't be preserved properly by my university	28	33.3
Other	6	7.1
Responses	84	

Other:

- My thesis will be embargoed at my supervisor's request so won't be visible anyway
- Degradation on image quality
- Superseded software codes, not matching the key word when searching in 10 years time ...
- None of the above really concern me. They all seem to be handled well by my university, or do not apply to my research
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future

Is there anything else that you would like to share about long-term access to and use of your PhD thesis?

- As my practice is cross-discipline-based, I intend to employ a multiplicity approach as I understand the fragility of research preservation.
- The physical body of work is an important component, intended for long term value for the historical record, so I want to ensure it is preserved safely
- My thesis will be embargoed because my supervisor does not want anyone outside the lab to access it
- It would be interesting to have a clearer by default link between a thesis and the publications directly originating from that thesis. Cambridge requires all publications to be open access so it should not be a big access problem.
- I will be used arXive and CERN documents server and the University repository to archive my thesis, but I worry about the search engine discoverability of these assets, and the way that permissions/copywrite could change over time (i.e., I want search engines to crawl my thesis but I wouldn't want AI models to be trained on it).
- Digital preservation is not a solved problem. Formats that were common in the 1990s when I was an undergraduate are now not necessarily supported or readable. The best advice from now (2026) may be invalid - probably not within 10 years, but within 100 years the recommended formats may be unsupported. We know that acid-free paper lasts over 100 years. We know that parchment lasts over 1000 years. Because the

formats and tools are all so recent, we have no knowledge of how to preserve an artefact for 100+ years.

- I have been warned against publishing my raw data by my supervisor, but I am concerned that to leave it out would undermine the validity of my findings. I am curious about what other PhD students have done with raw datasets and whether there are steps which can be taken to avoid plagiarism or intellectual theft.
- A workshop on research replicability will be great.
- The access point - easy to navigate
- If anything should be done on improving the long-term access, it should be combined with the knowledge on disseminating research results. Given everyone's going AI these days, it's important to know what do we have to give under the common open license terms for what we receive, how do we set a license terms for other users and what else can we keep private for our commercialisation or internal use. Otherwise there's no incentive for people to care about accessing a thesis many years down the line. There are already journal, conference and workshop papers that other users can easily search, cite and make use of. People often wrap up their thesis in a journal paper too.
- My thesis incorporates a 65-minute practice-based documentary, which is currently hosted on Vimeo with publicly accessible links. However, I am concerned that future changes in platform policies or the expiration of my personal Vimeo subscription may jeopardise continued access to these audiovisual research materials. I believe that the University could establish and provide a stable, permanent, and freely accessible institutional video repository, enabling readers to locate and consult these practice-based research outputs more reliably and conveniently.
- Don't want it to be accessed and reused in the future unless have to be published

Appendix B: Staff survey results

Which of the following best describes your main area(s) of responsibility?

Research data/repository management	59
Digital preservation	31
Technical/system support	9
Student services/support	7
Other	6
Responses	87

Other:

- Metadata management
- Archives
- Preservation/Digitization
- Open Research administration
- 1st year PGR
- PhD student

Institutional Policies and Practices

Is the submission of an electronic thesis a requirement for PhD students at your institution?

	No	%
Yes, the electronic thesis is required	79	90.8
Yes, both the electronic and print version of a thesis are required	3	3.4
No	1	1.1
Not sure	1	1.1
No, but submission of an electronic version is encouraged	0	0
Other	3	3.4
Total	87	100

Other:

- We receive these from universities;
- Yes, before we divested our doctoral programs;
- My org is a consortium – not tied to an individual institution

Does your institution formally recognise the preservation of electronic theses as a responsibility or priority?

	No	%
Yes	49	57.0
Not sure	20	23.3

No	13	15.1
Other	4	4.7
Total	86	100

Other:

- Our theses moved to electronic only in 2021 the institution hasn't necessarily come to terms with the change to the version of record
- There is an understanding of the obligation but it is not explicitly stated in any documentation
- The e-theses are located with the departments, and they are the ones responsible for looking after them.
- Yes, but nothing is in place

If yes, since when (please specify the year)?

41 responded usefully to this question. Ranging from 1960 to 2025. Appearing most often is 2012.

Which of the following preservation activities are undertaken at your institution for electronic theses?

Use of preservation metadata or documentation Integrity checks (e.g. checksums) to check that files remain unchanged over time	56
Preservation of supplementary files	56
Storing multiple copies across different storage locations	48
Storage in a dedicated digital preservation repository or system	40
Integrity checks (e.g., checksums) to check that files remain unchanged over time	28
Use of preservation metadata or documentation	27
Migration of e-theses to new file formats	12
Web archiving	8
Monitoring and management of access restrictions and embargoes	6
No preservation activities are in place for e-theses	6
Not sure	5
Other	0
Responses	87

Other:

- Not sure about multiple copies, integrity checks, or web archiving
- format submission validation
- Supplementary files are backed up but there can be obsolete formats
- Not some of these are being worked to/should be in place

Is the preservation of electronic theses covered in any of your institution's written policies?

	No	%
Yes	33	38.8
Not sure	25	29.4
No	21	24.7
Other	6	7.1
Total	85	100

Other:

- In progress
- Not specifically, but implied
- Not in formal institutional policy, but it is covered by library-specific procedures/guidelines
- Covered under larger University Policy
- We do have electronic document retention policies, but I don't know they would classify as "preservation" by archival standards

Which institutional policy or policies cover the preservation of electronic theses?

Thesis submission requirements	37
Institutional repository policy	37
Digital preservation policy	24
Research data management policy	7
Records management policy	7
Other	8
Responses	59

Other:

- No DP policy as yet
- Sort of a general library policy
- Archives policy
- Not sure any do
- Not sure about the research data and records management policies.
- Higher Degree by Research Examination Policy
- Open Access Policy
- Open Access Policy

Which types of materials does your institution accept as part of a PhD thesis submission?

A traditional text-based thesis	79
Text accompanied by supplementary files (e.g., datasets, software/code, multimedia)	71
A text-based thesis with embedded multimedia (e.g., audio, video, images)	51
A fully multimedia or non-text thesis	18
Not sure	4
Other types	2
Responses	86

Other:

- Music x 2
- Research
- Collection of published articles

Does your institution publish guidance or restrictions on the kinds of materials and/or file formats that can be submitted as part of an electronic thesis?

	No	%
Yes	45	52.3
No	27	31.4
Not sure	12	14.0
Other	2	2.3
Total	86	100

Other:

- Guidance, but not restrictions
- Provide consultative support to Graduate Faculty but no current published guidance

Do students at your institution need to provide specific metadata when submitting their electronic thesis? (Examples might include abstract, keywords, ORCID ID, supervisor, department, rights information, etc)

	No	%
Yes, there are clearly defined metadata requirements for all PhD students	54	63.5
The inclusion of metadata alongside thesis submission is encouraged but no fields are mandatory	10	11.8
No, there are no formal metadata requirements	7	8.2
Yes, but the requirements vary by department or faculty	6	7.1
Not sure	5	5.9
Other	3	3.5
Total	85	100

Other:

- We accept metadata from universities (ETD-MS from their repositories via OAI-PMH)
- Metadata is gathered through the submission process
- We do not take theses

Does your institution provide guidance or procedures for handling sensitive data in electronic theses? (Examples might include personal data, confidential research, etc)

	No	%
Yes, formal policies and/or procedures exist and are clearly documented	40	47.1
Yes, general guidance is provided informally or as recommendations	25	29.4
Not sure	12	14.1
No, there is no guidance	6	7.1
Other	2	2.4
Total	85	100

Other:

- This responsibility is delegated to individual campuses
- It depends what the IRB is approved for

Which of the following areas are covered by your institution's guidance on sensitive data?

Embargoes or restricted access options	66
Anonymisation or redaction of data	49
Roles and responsibilities for students, supervisors and/or staff	36
How to identify sensitive data	34
Metadata/documentation for sensitive data	17
Other	3
Responses	74

Other:

- Provided via data management training
- Not sure
- Unsure

Student Needs and Support

In your view, which aspects do PhD students most need additional guidance regarding the the preservation of electronic theses? (Select up to three)

Understanding copyright and intellectual property rights associated with their work and third-party content	65
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Identifying sensitive content and applying appropriate embargoes, redaction, or restricted access	42
Choosing file formats that are suitable for long-term preservation and use	24
Knowing what is required during submission and who is responsible for each step	24
Understanding which components are considered part of the thesis (e.g., text, multimedia, datasets, etc.)	19
Strategies for maintaining the integrity and accessibility of their thesis post-submission	19
How to create and record metadata to support discoverability, context, and preservation	16
Guidance on including embedded content or external links in a way that preserves them over time	13
Other	11
Responses	84

Other:

- Unknown - not the area I work in
- Digital accessibility standards/techniques
- How to follow directions
- Ensuring their sources remain accessible over time

Does your institution provide training or guidance to PhD students on how to prepare their electronic thesis in ways that support long-term preservation and accessibility?

	No	%
No	31	37.3
Yes, but guidance is provided informally and/or varies by department	17	20.5
Yes, formal guidance or training is provided	16	19.3
Not sure	14	16.9
Other	5	6.0
Total	83	100

Other:

- No, but we will be in the coming year
- We provide guidance on how to submit their work to ProQuest, I then get the thesis and do the rest - including publishing works as Open Access and depositing files with metadata into our digital preservation system
- We provide general training suitable for this group
- Training to use Word to format the thesis and training on the deposit process but not specifically preservation
- Told to save as PDF/A but no other guidance

How is guidance or training related to the preservation and accessibility of electronic theses typically delivered to students?

Written guidance published or distributed online	37
One-on-one support on request	37
Provided informally or on an ad hoc basis	27
In-person workshops or training sessions	26
Online training modules	18
Included as part of broader research skills or doctoral training programs	14
Not applicable, no training or guidance is provided	11
Not sure	10
Other (please specify)	1
Responses	78

Other: Varies by institution

Based on your experience, which formats or approaches do PhD students at your institution generally find most helpful or engaging when receiving training or guidance on any topic? (Select up to three)

One-to-one support or consultations	41
In-person workshops or training sessions	27
Live online sessions (webinars)	26
Written guidance or handbooks	23
Checklists or quick-reference guides	23
Online training modules	20
Not sure	19
Video tutorials	7
Other	2
Responses	78

Other:

- We receive from universities (no direct interaction with students)
- Varies by institution

Based on your experience, what factors most commonly prevent PhD students from engaging with training or guidance offered at your institution? (Select up to three)

Lack of awareness about what training or guidance is available	55
Lack of time	40
Training is not perceived as relevant or important	28
Timing (training offered too early/late in the PhD)	24
Not sure	16

Training materials are too difficult to find or access	7
Training format or mode of delivery does not meet student needs	4
Other	3
Responses	79

Other:

- We receive from universities (no direct interaction with students)
- Varies by institution

At what stage in the PhD process do you or your team typically become involved in supporting students with thesis submission or the preservation of their electronic thesis?

At the point of thesis submission	43
After submission	27
In the final year before submission	20
Only when students seek support	17
At the start of the PhD (e.g., induction or early training)	12
Not sure	9
During the middle stages of the PhD	4
Responses	79

Copyright, Rights, and Content Challenges

Which of the following areas do students most commonly struggle with? (Select up to three)

Understanding embargo requirements or restricted access requirements	42
Clearing rights for third-party content	39
Including work previously published by the student	23
Providing accurate rights information during submission	20
Using research data collected by the student (for example: interview data, survey responses, images, recordings, or other data requiring consent, anonymisation, or rights clearance)	17
Licensing their own thesis	17
Not sure	12
Other	4
None of these	1
Responses	79

Other:

- We receive from universities (no direct interaction with students)
- Identifying the inclusion of personal information, ensuring that their data is fit and permitted to be shared publicly

- Digital accessibility checks/standards; formatting!

Common Barriers

In your view, what are the main barriers or challenges to effective preservation of electronic theses at your institution? (Select up to three)

Limited staff time or resources to manage preservation activities	58
Lack of formal policies or guidance on preservation	31
Students' lack of awareness or understanding of preservation requirements	21
Technical limitations of repository or storage systems	21
Lack of training or guidance for staff	19
Issues with files formats, multimedia, or embedded content	14
Copyright, intellectual property, or licensing concerns	14
Sensitive or confidential data restrictions	8
Not sure	6
Other	6
Inconsistent metadata or documentation from students	3
Responses	79

Other:

- Our team is involved only after submission, we depend on other for the training and rules
- Lack of updates to our formal policies in a changing field, many stakeholders involved, but no one to take on that responsibility clearly
- Institution not yet ready for non standard formats
- Poor integration of digital preservation unit with faculty of graduate studies as well as lack of interest from faculty of graduate study
- Dispersed ownership and responsibility: thesis submission recently transferred to the centre away from the Library; the Library is responsible for preservation of content but has not yet established a preservation layer for eTheses. A project is planned to explore this
- We have no remit for this

Is there anything else you would like to share about supporting students with the preparation, submission, or long-term preservation of their electronic theses? For example, what do you wish students understood better, or what kinds of training or guidance would help move things forward at your institution?

- While we received both a print and an electronic version of theses the print copy was understood as the version of record, electronic copies sometimes had redacted sections

where rights couldn't be obtained or so sensitive material wasn't placed online. With the sudden switch to electronic only during Covid no real thought was given to whether a version of record electronic copy that contained the full thesis was being kept, library staff don't really know if they are only receiving a redacted copy or whether the copy they receive matches the copy held by the PhD management system (which they have no access to) and there is no Masters management system.

- In my opinion, students are largely unaware of the benefits of digital preservation unless it relates to research datasets. I don't necessarily regard this as problematic, as I believe the responsibility should largely fall to the academic institution to preserve scholarly output.
- We keep theses in our institutional repository, but there are no distinct 'preservation' actions taken beyond that. Only theses that are confidential are held specifically in our preservation system, so that they are not made public.
- We take the approach that it's better to do some preservation activities than none. It would be helpful to understand more around best practice in metadata and file formats for preservation, as we don't have a lot of internal expertise in this area.
- We need training for students, but with all the training that already exists, they won't see that training on preservation is important. We also have issues with the format used; we require PDFs, but they can be created with any software. We also have challenges with withdrawal requests... So many challenges of all kinds!
- Better pro-active engagement with students about copyright, sensitive materials, and non-standard digital formats
- I wish students had training on all the components of thesis preparation at the *beginning* of their degree. It feels like failure when they are learning about this while they are scrambling to submit, and that happens often.
- Our process for submission is handled by a different office that uses a 3rd party tool we have no control over. Submission, review, and preliminary publication is all controlled outside of Libraries by non-repository staff. ETDs (electronic theses and dissertations) are only sent to the IR (and therefore to our preservation environment) after initial publication in the vendor system. We've found this means that items need significant re-cataloguing before they can be ingested into the IR, and that (as the most public face of published ETDs) we get questions and requests from authors that we are not able to help with. On the positive side, this division of labour means that we rarely

need to deal directly with embargoed or otherwise restricted materials, as that is all handled on the submission side and in the vendor's system.

- I think we've switched from being concerned about preservation to being concerned about accessibility. Our theses and dissertations exist only in the electronic format, and are only held by our statewide system, the OhioLINK ETD Center. We do not have a local storage process at all. This gives (at least) our archivist and myself periodic fits of anxiety, but we currently do not have the time or staff or infrastructure to build a process for local long-term storage, whether that's electronic or in print.
- Knowledge of preservation activities needs to be embedded in the researcher journey for doctoral students rather than being considered only at the submission end point. This means that teaching and training offered throughout the PhD lifecycle must be supported by academic departments.
- It's important to build checks within the submission process so that materials problems are identified early on. Is the thesis actually a PDF, and can it be opened?
- We're only at the starting point of digitally preserving theses, and lack a policy statement for doing so. Having policy for this as well as for research data would be extremely helpful as it would get the Library involved earlier in the process and impress the need for digital preservation for these early career researchers.
- Collaboration between faculties, the thesis office, teaching and learning services and the library would make the entire process more manageable. There is a lack of communication internally that leads to a lack of understanding of who is expected to provide which services. This then becomes confusing for the students. If each group involved would provide a service that was cohesive and not independent of the others, the system would work better and students would know to whom to direct their questions.